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The use of indicators to assess innovation development: A panel data analysis

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Abstract

The aim of this article is to identify the indicators with the best predictive power to explain variations in innovation across the years from a country-level perspective. For such, the Global Innovation Index (GII) from 2013 to 2021 was used to carry out the necessary quantitative analysis. Output-related variables proved to be the most relevant in terms of predictive power throughout the years. However, when considering solemnly the knowledge and technology and creative outputs as dependent variables, business sophistication was the most representative.

Keywords: Global Innovation Index. Innovation indicators. Innovation inputs. Innovation outputs. Panel regression analysis.

Introduction & Context

For a long time, measuring innovation was a priority for policy makers and researchers around the world; thus, it is understood that there are ongoing discussions about what would be the best indicators to measure innovation (Corrente, Garcia-Bernabeu, Greco & Makkonen, 2021). Innovation is a complex phenomenon that involves private and public players, academia, science and technology parks, policies, among others – there is, therefore, no consensus about the best indicators to measure innovation (Corrente et al., 2021).

Despite such difficulty in and measuring innovation, there are a few initiatives targeted at addressing such conundrum. One example is the European Innovation Scoreboard, which aims to measure the performance of innovation across European countries, highlighting the strengths and weaknesses of national innovation systems. The OECD also provides interesting data regarding business innovation statistics and indicators, covering OECD member countries and partner economies. Another example of such initiative is that of the Global Innovation Index (GII), on which the present article will focus. This index has been developed through a partnership between the Cornell University, INSEAD and the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) and has been monitoring the progress of countries in terms of innovation

development since 2007. As it is considered an index with robust indicators to measure innovation that has already been widely used in academia (e.g., Dogval, Goncharenko, Honcharenko, Shuba & Babenko, 2019; Sendra-Pons, Comeig & Mas-Tur, 2022; Todeva, 2020, among others), we chose to use it as a source of secondary data.

There is a positive relationship between innovation and the development of science and technology, they can be considered intertwined processes. In this way, an innovation system considers business, science and education as key players for the development of innovation (Chulok, 2021), and innovation arises from the interaction between knowledge and technology (Daraei & Rahimikia, 2022). A country can, therefore, enhance innovation by using multifaceted incentives for the development of science and technology which should be expressed by proper indicators (Raghupathi & Raghupathi, 2019).

Keeping this in mind that there are several indicators available to measure and to assess innovation performance, we intend to answer the following research question: Which are the most relevant variables capable of explaining variations in innovation across time and how to they relate to innovation inputs and outputs?

Even though there are several studies that utilize the GII to carry out analyses, whether qualitative (e.g., Sendra-Pons, Comeig & Mas-Tur, 2022; Todeva, 2020) or quantitative (Faghih & Sazegar, 2019; Franco & Oliveira, 2017), we came across no research that assessed the GII in isolation to verify the most representative indicators capable of explaining the variations observed in innovation performance across countries and throughout the years. Thus, this research was developed to fill this gap identified in the literature. The findings of this research may be useful for policy makers in the field of innovation at national and regional levels for designing measures for supporting innovation, as policies could focus more on the strengths of innovation, as the most relevant variables will be highlighted to better understand the shades embedded in the phenomenon.

Method

We will carry out herein three multiple linear regression analyses using panel data covering the years 2013 to 2021. The data comprehend the innovation performance of 131 countries across this specific time frame; therefore, the number of observations used in this study 1,179. Even though the GII monitors countries since 2007, some of the pillars have changed over the years and the tabulated data were made available only from 2013 onwards. This explains why the years 2007 to 2012 were not considered in the present analysis.

The GII somehow neglected the link between innovation and global challenges (Todeva, 2020). However, despite this criticism and the absence of weight attributed to significant players in triple and quadruple helix models (Corrente et al., 2021), the “methodological approach of the GII enables cross-country comparability at multiple levels – the level of the overall ranking, the level of sub-indices, the level of input and output categories, and the level of individual indicators” (Todeva, 2020: 128).

Moreover, the GII considers several indicators that constitute the seven pillars of innovation, not only the GDP, which would lead to incorrect and biased predictions that do not take into account the complexity involved in innovation processes (Kruss, Sithole, & Buchana, 2020). Figure 1 shows the pillars presented by GII, which are divided into input and outputs of innovation.

Figure 1. Innovation inputs and outputs.

The input indicators can be understood as inductors of innovation, whereas outputs are the result, i.e., innovation itself. Figure 2 illustrates the sub-pillars pertaining to each pillar of the GII.

Figure 2. Pillars and sub-pillars.

The panel regression analysis was chosen as the most appropriate technique to answer the research question, as we intent to analyze herein cross sectional and longitudinal panel data. For such, data were collected over time (from 2013 to 2021) and over the same 131 individuals, i.e., the number of countries with complete data in every GII report. Moreover, panel data analysis provides several data points and reduces multicollinearity issues among the

explanatory variables, improving the efficiency of estimates and allowing the multidimensional investigation of a phenomenon (Raghupathi & Raghupathi, 2019). The panel data regression model was built with Python.

To answer the research question proposed herein and to provide further information on the relationship between dependent and independent(s) variable(s), we will carry out the three panel regression analyses with three different purposes.

First regression analysis. In this analysis, the GII will be considered the dependent variable to analyze the indicators (or pillars) that mostly affected its development over time. This analysis will provide a wider picture of what has been really the most relevant indicator (s) to innovation since 2013 according to the annual GII reports.

Second regression analysis. The purpose of this regression is to analyze the variables that most influence the knowledge and technology outputs throughout the years.

Third regression analysis. Similar to the second analysis, the third panel regression analysis will analyze the variables mostly related to the creative outputs.

Analysis & Discussion

We begin the data analysis by presenting the assumptions involved in the multiple linear regression technique, which were considered for the three panel analyses. Figure 3 shows that the variables have a linear distribution.

Figure 3. Linearity of correlations

The collinearity test performed indicates the absence of multicollinearity problems, even through three of them present approximate collinearity, i.e., with values closer to 1, in the cross correlations. The value of the Durbin-Watson test was 2.052, indicating little to no autocorrelation.

Figure 4. Collinearity test.

The distribution of the residuals does not vary much along the axis, thus indicating small heteroscedasticity (Figure 5). Furthermore, the residuals also presented a normal distribution, which is line with the assumption of the regression analysis (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Distribution of residuals.

Figure 6. Normality of residuals.

After the accomplishment of the tests to ensure the compliance with all assumptions of multiple linear regression, we will proceed with the outcomes of the panel analyses. Table 1 indicates

the outcomes of the first panel regression analysis. In this regression, the GII overall score was considered the dependent variable; the seven innovation pillars (institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, business sophistication, knowledge and technology outputs, and creative outputs) were the independent variables.

Table 1. First panel regression analysis – GII as dependent variable.

Index	Sum_sq	df	F	p-value
Residual	2034.524561	123	NaN	NaN
Institutions	496.3609005	1	30.00818567	2.32E-07
Human Capital	968.8381864	1	58.57245434	4.92E-12
Infrastructure	454.6647129	1	27.4873849	6.67E-07
Market_Soph	846.3658747	1	51.16822112	6.66E-11
Business_Soph	254.0210331	1	15.35719336	0.0001467579194
Knowledge_Out	2729.023078	1	164.9868697	1.79E-24
Creative_Out	3916.647523	1	236.7863503	1.89E-30

Creative and knowledge and technology outputs have the best predictive power to explain the variance of innovation over the years, which is expected, as the outputs can be considered innovation itself. Table 2 shows all pillars in descending order according to their respective predictive power.

Table 2. Ranking of the pillars.

Pillar	Position
Creative outputs	1
Knowledge and technology outputs	2
Human capital and research	3
Market sophistication	4
Infrastructure	5
Institutions	6
Business sophistication	7

Even though the institutional framework may be considered as a crucial player in the promotion of entrepreneurship, varying according to the socioeconomic characteristics of each country (Sendra-Pons, Comeig & Mas-Tur, 2022), the institutional performance and business sophistication across the years, in this regression analysis, played a less relevant role in terms of innovation scores.

The upcoming analysis considers the pillar knowledge and technology outputs as dependent variable; institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication are the independent variables.

Table 3. Second panel data analysis – Knowledge and technology outputs as dependent variable.

Index	Sum_sq	df	F	P-value
Institutions	58.68941	1	0.1310543571	0.7179526127
Human Capital	4284.859072	1	9.568156351	0.00244265811
Infrastructure	1858.678925	1	4.150458688	0.04373439226
Market_Soph	281.0175428	1	0.6275165045	0.4297685206
Business_Soph	6007.953261	1	13.41585223	0.0003669944186
Residual	55978.11786	125	NaN	NaN

The outcomes of the second panel data analysis are somewhat different from that of the first regression. Here, business sophistication was the variable presenting the best predictive power amongst all innovation inputs, followed by human capital, infrastructure and market sophistication (on the verge of the 0.05 threshold). In this model, institution-related variables should not be considered as good predictors, as the p-value was above 0.05.

Table 4 presents the third and final panel data analysis, with creative outputs as dependent variable, and the innovation inputs as independent variables.

Table 4. Third panel data analysis – Creative outputs as dependent variable.

index	Sum_sq	df	F	P-value
Institutions	1441.564694	1	4.44345812	0.03703232215
Human Capital	406.8799488	1	1.254160857	0.2649064485
Infrastructure	2769.655793	1	8.537146876	0.004130674202
Market_Soph	640.5008353	1	1.974270492	0.1624756478
Business_Soph	5844.222632	1	18.01414714	4.24E-05
Residual	40553.00666	125	NaN	NaN

Even though the p-values found in this analysis were different from those presented in Table 3, the best predictor remained the same: Business sophistication. The other variables with higher predictive power, in descending order, were infrastructure, institutions, market sophistication and human capital. Unlike the second regression model, all innovation inputs were maintained here.

The findings presented so far lead to a few interesting insights. First, the results of the first regression shows that the outputs of innovation are the best predictors of innovation performance for countries. It is important to highlight, nevertheless, that the first panel regression does not indicate that the other pillars are not good predictors of innovation; the analysis categorizes the variables according to their predictive power.

Second, business sophistication ranked last in the first panel regression analysis, but was considered the strongest predictor in the other regressions two regressions, i.e., the panel regressions that had the innovation outputs as dependent variables.

An explanation for such could be that business sophistication is more related to the intangible aspect of innovation outputs, which is in line with (Parrilli, Balavac & Radicic, 2020) when affirming that innovation based on learning-by-doing learning-by-using, and learning-by-interacting proved to be more important for innovation outputs than traditional science and technology-based innovation. Business sophistication comprises other three sub-pillars, namely knowledge workers, innovation linkages and knowledge absorption.

Alarcón, Aguilar and Galán (2018) also emphasize the importance of cooperation for innovation outputs in Spanish firms. A positive relationship between networks and innovation output in large connected components was also found by Zhang, Duan and Zhou (2017). Considering absorptive capacity, Murovec and Prodan (2009) proved that its most important determinants were internal R&D, training of personnel, innovation co-operation and attitude toward change; i.e., concepts also related to intangible assets. Therefore, the outcomes of the panel regression analyses are in line with previous findings.

Even though the study of Yu, Huarng & Lai (2021) used a fsQCA to analyze some pillars of the GII, the study did not have a quantitative focus and did not carry out a panel data analysis. By analyzing the input and output variables of the GII, the authors show the common causal combination of high GII: High Institutions AND High Human capital and research AND High Infrastructure AND High Business sophistication AND High Knowledge and technology outputs AND High Creative outputs. Such combination covers all pillars, except for market sophistication, which is not supported by any of the three panel regression analyses carried out here.

Final considerations

This research brought some important contributions to the field of innovation studies in terms of use of indicators to assess innovation performance over time. Through the three panel regression analyses accomplished here, some important findings were reached, which deserve to be highlighted in this final part of the article.

Even though the innovation outputs had the best predictive power in the first regression, innovation is not something that appears in isolation; there is a lot of institutional support, human capital, and adequate infrastructure that enable its development. However, when evaluating only the variance of innovation over the years, the outputs are considered the best variables to explain such variability. In this way, increases in creative and knowledge and technology outputs will lead to an increase in the innovation score of the GII; lower scores of creative and knowledge outputs, in turn, will imply in a decrease in the overall innovation score.

In addition, another important finding was the importance given to business sophistication in both regression analyses that had the innovation outputs as dependent variables. This may be because the variables covered by the business sophistication pillar are the ones that encompass indicators related to intangible assets, especially the sub-pillar innovation linkages, which involves university-industry R&D collaboration, state of cluster development, gross expenditure on R&D financed from abroad, joint venture and strategic alliances, and patent families. This is also supported by literature, as seen in the previous section, which establishes a positive and significant relationship between innovation outputs and collaboration.

Moreover, this research supports that innovation has a direct impact on the sustainability of a country's economic growth, which is why it is crucial to adopt strong policies that encourage more research and development (Mohamed, Liu & Nie, 2022).

This article presents a few limitations. This study only comprehended the years between 2013 and 2021. Future studies can look at a longer span, thus enabling the identification of other patterns in the data. Another limitation is the fact that this study focused only on the GII, thus neglecting other possible indicators at the country-level that could be considered in order to determine and assess innovation performance.

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